

ISic1112

I.Sicily inscription 1112

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Calatafimi, Biblioteca comunale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140595

1. ἱερομναμονέων
2. Τίττελος Ἀρτεμιδώρο [υ]
3. τὰν ἐπιμέλειαν ἐποιήσα [το]
4. τῶν ἔργων τοῦ ἀνδρεῶνο [ς]
5. [κ]αὶ τᾶς προέδρας μετὰ τ [ῶν]
6. ἱεροφυλάκων.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492728

EDCS 39102269

PHI 140595

Bibliography

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